

Metal Complexes of 2-Amino-1-Cyclopentene-1-Dithiocarboxylate

Khirod Chandra Pattnaik and Debabrata Sen

A series of compounds of bivalent metal ions such as Ni(II), Co(II), Pt(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Fe(II), with 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylate, have been isolated in the solid state. They have been characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility determination and infrared spectral analysis. Square planar stereochemistry has been assigned to the bis chelates, ML_2 , formed by all the bivalent metal ions except Fe(II). The latter forms an octahedral, spin-free compound having the composition, $NH_4 [FeL_3]$.

In a recent communication¹ the synthesis of ammonium 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylate has been reported. The reagent which gives intense coloured complexes with various bi- and trivalent metal ions, has been shown to be extremely sensitive for the detection of nickel ion in solution². It was thought interesting to study the chemical and physical characteristics of these metal complexes and to suggest probable structures for them.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ligand, ammonium salt of 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylate was prepared following the method given in the literature¹. It was purified by recrystallisation from ethyl alcohol.

Bis(2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylato)nickel(II)/zinc(II)/cadmium(II) : The complexes with Ni(II), Zn(II), and Cd(II) were prepared by the addition of an aqueous solution of the ammonium salt of the ligand to the aqueous solution of the corresponding metal chlorides/nitrates. The compounds having the general formula ML_2 separated out almost quantitatively. They were filtered, washed with ethyl alcohol and dried in a desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$. These complexes are insoluble in water, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, and sparingly soluble in nitrobenzene. Conductance measurements in nitrobenzene indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes. The compounds are stable under usual laboratory conditions and can be kept for a long time without apparent decomposition.

Bis(2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylato)cobalt(II) : The compound had been prepared by the interaction of cobalt(II) chloride with the ammonium salt of the ligand in aqueous media when a brown compound precipitated out. This was filtered, washed with ethyl alcohol and water and then dried over fused $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator. The compound shows paramagnetic behaviour ($\mu_{eff} = 2.17$ B.M.). On keeping exposed to air, the complex is slowly oxidised to a Co(III) species which, however, could not be isolated in the pure state. On exposure to air, magnetic susceptibility of the Co(II) complex slowly decreases until it is finally converted to the diamagnetic cobalt(III) complex.

1. T. Takeshima, *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 730.

2. M. Yokoyama and T. Takeshima, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 1344,

Ammonium tris(2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylato)iron(II): The compound was prepared by the interaction of ferrous ammonium sulphate and the ammonium salt of the ligand in aqueous solution. The resulting dark green solid was filtered, washed with ethyl alcohol and water and dried over fused CaCl_2 in a desiccator. The compound is stable in air for few days but changes to a pasty mass on keeping. The compound is insoluble in most polar and non-polar solvents but sparingly soluble in nitrobenzene. The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.87$ B.M.).

Bis(2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylato) platinum(II): The complex separated out slowly on mixing aqueous solutions of the ammonium salt of the ligand and potassium chloroplatinate. The quadrivalent platinum was reduced to the bivalent state resulting in the formation of the compound having composition, Pt(II)L_2 .

The physical and chemical properties of the complex are analogous to those of Ni(II) complex.

The data on elemental analysis and magnetic properties are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Metal		Sulphur		μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
NiL_2	Reddish violet	14.94	15.64	33.54	34.17	diamagnetic
CoL_2	Brown	15.36	15.69	34.01	34.15	2.17
$\text{NH}_4[\text{FeL}_3]$	Greenish yellow	9.60	10.17	32.92	33.24	4.87
PtL_2	Red	36.80	38.16	24.65	25.04	diamagnetic
ZnL_2	Yellow	17.00	17.11	33.39	33.58	,,
CdL_2	Yellow	26.10	26.20	29.59	29.90	,,

'L' represents the ligand, 2-amino-1-cyclopentene-1-dithiocarboxylate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{NS}_2$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The elemental analysis and diamagnetic behaviour indicate square-planar configuration for the Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pt(II) complexes having the general formula ML_2 . The magnetic susceptibility corresponding to an effective moment value of 2.17 B.M., suggests that the cobalt(II) complex has spin-paired and square-planar configuration. This compound, on standing, gradually changes to an octahedral, diamagnetic cobalt(III) complex. An octahedral spin-free Fe(II) compound, $\text{NH}_4[\text{FeL}_3]$ having an effective moment value of 4.87 B.M. has also been isolated.

Structurally sensitive infrared bands of the ligand and of its metal complexes are recorded in Table II. The infrared spectra of the ligand and its metal complexes show the characteristic group frequencies such as asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations and deformation vibration of the NH_2 group, $\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\text{C}-\text{N}$, $\text{C}\cdots\text{S}$ stretching vibrations etc. Two or more bands, observed in the region $3100\text{--}3480\text{ cm}^{-1}$, are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of NH_2 group and the $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretch. In the

metal complexes these bands are shifted to some lower frequency below 3350 cm^{-1} . This observation suggests that the NH_2 group is involved in co-ordination with the metal ions. It is well known from the infrared spectral studies of several amino complexes³ that non co-ordinating amino groups show $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ bands above 3370 cm^{-1} and co-ordinated NH_2 groups show the bands below this region.

TABLE II

Ligand	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$	δNH_2	C = C	C—N/C=S	C ... S
	3480-s	1647-s	1538-m	1370-s	795-s
	3279-s		1460-s	1319-ms	
	3106-s		1449-s	1290-s	
			1418-s		
NiL_2	3175-ms	1613-s	1504-m(sh)	1333-ms	806-w
			1471-s	1382-m	
			1431-sh		
			1408-m		
	3356-s	1613-s	1515-s	1316-s	820-s
CoL_2	3226-s		1471-s	1282-ms	
	3125-s		1418-sh		
$\text{NH}_4[\text{FeL}_3]$	3145-s	1613-s	1504-m	1304-m	813-m
			1449-s	1274-m	
			1429-sh		
			1393-sh		
	3333-s	1613-s	1504-sh	1333-s	816-m
PtL_2	3226-s		1471-s	1290-s	
	3125-ms		1389-m		
ZnL_2	3289-s	1600-s	1460-s	1379-s	840-w
				1266-s	
CdL_2	3279-s	1600-s	1493-w	1379-m	830-m
	3125-m		1449-s	1266-m	

The ligand shows a strong band at 795 cm^{-1} which is attributed to C ... S stretching vibration. It is shifted to higher frequency region in all the metal complexes. It indicates that the ligand is co-ordinated to metal ion through the NH_2 and C ... S group. The structures of the ligand and the metal complexes may be represented as

3. L. J. Bellamy, The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules, Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1959, 355.

One of the two bands located in the region $1270\text{--}1320\text{ cm}^{-1}$, may be attributed to the C = S stretching vibration. Of these, the lower frequency band is more sensitive to co-ordination than the higher frequency band. The lowering of this band frequency in some complexes may be due to flow of electrons to produce C \cdots S in preference to C = S on complex formation. It is also indicated by the corresponding shift of the C \cdots S stretching bands to higher frequencies in all the metal complexes. In the cases of Zn(II), and Cd(II) complexes these effects are more pronounced. In these cases, polymerization through the formation of C = S \cdots M bonds, is also a distinct possibility. However, molecular weights of the compounds could not be determined due to their inadequate solubility in common solvents.

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Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory,
Indian Institute of Technology,
Kharagpur-2, West Bengal.

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